

The Psychological Literature On The Formation Of Life Strategies In Students

Khudoyberganov Doniyorbek Yangiboy oglu

Independent researcher at Urgench State University named after Abu Rayhon Beruni

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18080357>

Annotation: This article analyzes the issue of the formation of life strategies in students from a psychological perspective. The article discusses the concept of life strategies, the pedagogical and psychological foundations of their development, as well as the mechanisms for the formation of such competencies as decision-making, problem solving and social adaptation in students. The results of the study show their impact on the personal development of students, their ability to self-manage and future professional success.

Keywords: student, life strategies, personal development, psychological competencies, decision-making, problem solving, social adaptation.

Introduction.

The issue of the formation of life strategies in students is seen as a complex scientific problem located at the intersection of modern psychology, pedagogy and sociology. A deep understanding of the theoretical and practical aspects of this problem requires, first of all, a systematic analysis of how it is covered in the psychological literature. Because the ideas about the student's life strategy have been interpreted differently in different periods and scientific schools: some researchers see it as a strategic direction related to the long-term goals and plans of the individual, others interpret it as a mechanism of social adaptation, and a third group of scientists interpret it as a psychological expression of the process of personal growth and self-realization.

In Western psychological literature, the issue of life strategies is studied more within the framework of categories such as life planning, life goals, future orientation, career decision-making, self-determination. Representatives of humanistic psychology (A. Maslow, K. Rogers, etc.) see the processes of a person's self-awareness, self-actualization, and search for the meaning of life as the main factors determining the life strategy. Also, studies on motivation theories, future orientation, identification and career choice are directly related to the formation of life strategies in students and have created a certain theoretical basis in this regard.

Within the framework of the CIS and Russian psychological schools, many studies have been conducted on concepts such as life strategy, life path, life plan, personal goal system, social activity, professional self-determination. These approaches usually pay special attention to the interaction of the individual with social conditions, historical and cultural factors, social roles and statuses, psychological mechanisms of professional decisions, as well as the psychological characteristics of

adolescence. The student period is often seen as a turning point in the life path, and it is at this stage that the formation of a person's future strategy, professional and social position is emphasized.

In studies conducted in Uzbekistan and in Central Asia in general, students' attitudes towards life, profession, and their place in society are often studied in close connection with factors such as spiritual and moral values, national mentality, family and neighborhood institutions, and youth policy during the period of independence. Life strategies are interpreted as a set of personal and social views that are directly formed on the basis of such factors. However, in the psychological literature, there are relatively few works that address the issue of "formation of life strategies in students" as a separate, complex psychological and pedagogical problem, which further increases the relevance of this issue. Therefore, this paragraph will consider the theoretical approaches, conceptual models, main concepts and categories put forward in relation to the formation of life strategies in students through a comparative analysis of Western, Russian, and Uzbek psychological sources. First of all, the content of categories close to the concept of "life strategy" (life path, life goals, professional self-determination, future orientation, meaning of life, etc.) is clarified. Then, which aspects of these categories are relevant in the context of the psychological characteristics specific to the student period are separately analyzed.

This literature review serves, on the one hand, to reconstruct the general picture of existing scientific views, and on the other hand, to identify the studied and insufficiently covered aspects of the problem of forming life strategies in students. Thus, a comparative analysis of psychological literature serves as a methodological foundation for theoretical generalization and practical research conducted in the following chapters.

Approaches of Western European and American researchers.

In Western psychology, the issue of forming life strategies is studied inextricably linked with the processes of personal development, motivation, professional self-determination, future orientation and identification. In these studies, the term "life strategy" is more often expressed in such categories as life planning, career strategy, future orientation, self-determination, personal life goals.

In A. Maslow's ideas about self-actualization, a person's life strategy is associated with his striving for personal perfection, his natural need to fully realize his potential. According to Maslow, as a person accepts responsibility for his choices, he approaches conscious planning of his life, which forms the psychological foundation of a life strategy. K. Rogers also shows the process of a person's "self-awareness" and finding his "true self" as the central point of the life path.

In Kulgan's research on future orientation, young people's visions of the future are interpreted as an internal psychological mechanism that regulates their current

activities. In E. Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, the youth period is associated with identification, and the person's answer to the questions "who he wants to be" determines the content of the life strategy.

Professional development theorists such as D. Super, J. Holland, Savickas mainly illuminate life strategies through models related to choosing a profession, determining a career direction, and imagining oneself in a professional role. They see the student period as the most important stage of professional identification.

In general, in Western literature, a student's life strategy is interpreted as a complex psychological process associated with a system of personal goals, decision-making processes, internal motivation and future planning.

Approaches in research of the CIS and Russian psychological schools.

In the Russian psychological school, the issue of life strategy is often addressed in connection with such categories as life path, life plans, personal goal system, professional self-determination, and social activity of the individual. In the approach of representatives of this school, socio-cultural factors, living conditions of the individual, social roles and historical context play an important role.

S. L. Rubinstein's activity approach interprets a person's life path as a system associated with his activities, choices and social relations. According to Rubinstein, in order for a person to be the subject of his own life, he must be able to consciously organize the processes of choice, which is the basis of the life strategy.

B. G. Ananyev, considering the life path of a person in combination with his psychophysiological, social and cultural aspects, assessed the student period as the most active stage in the maturation of the personality and the formation of a future strategy.

L. I. Bozhovich's research on the motivational sphere shows that the role of stable motives, internal needs and value systems in the formation of a life strategy in students is very important. According to Bozhovich, the "meaningful motives" of a person are the main psychological foundation of a life strategy.

In the CIS literature, life strategies are interpreted more based on approaches related to socialization, the assimilation of social roles by the individual and adaptation to the requirements of society. The ratio of individual decisions to social factors is widely covered.

Approaches in the research of psychologists and educators of Uzbekistan.

In Uzbek psychological and pedagogical literature, the issue of life strategies is interpreted as being inextricably linked to the individual's spiritual and moral value system, the influence of family and society, national mentality, social activity of young people, and professional self-determination.

The studies of psychologists such as M. Karimova, R. Sunnatova, N. Okhunov cover issues such as a person's attitude to life, goal setting, social activity, and

psychological adaptation of young people. According to their general conclusion, the life strategy of students is a psychological process that is formed on the basis of a person's ability to plan their own life, the harmony of social values, and personal needs.

In Uzbek studies, the student period is often seen as a process associated with a person's striving for spiritual perfection, assimilation of national values, and finding their own professional path. In this approach, the life strategy is interpreted not just as a system of individual choices, but as a factor determining the person's responsibility to society and social position.

In studies on youth policy (A. Jo'rayev, Sh. Shorahmedov, B. Kadyrov, etc.), pedagogical and social mechanisms for purposeful guidance of students, formation of their vision of the future, and support for professional self-determination are widely covered. In them, life strategy is associated with national values, the role of the family institution, and personal responsibility.

Analysis of the coverage of the formation of life strategies in students in the psychological literature shows that this issue has been studied by various scientific schools from different theoretical perspectives. In Western psychology, life strategy is interpreted as a process associated with an individual's independent decision-making, internal motivation, self-actualization, and conscious planning of the future. In this approach, a person's subjective experience, free choice, and personal goals play a central role.

The CIS and Russian psychological schools explain life strategy as a process of socialization of the individual, the assimilation of social roles, professional self-determination and planning of his life path. In this approach, there is a strong tendency to link the socio-cultural context, the interaction of the individual with society and the life path with historical conditions. Life strategies are explained more by the social adaptation of the individual, the ability to meet the demands of society.

In the psychological literature of Uzbekistan, the issue of life strategy is interpreted inextricably linked with spiritual and moral values, national mentality, the role of the family institution, the spiritual maturity of the individual and the processes of professional self-determination. In the formation of students' life strategies, components such as social responsibility, perfection, patriotism, and loyalty to national values are of particular importance. In this approach, both the internal psychological processes of the individual and socio-cultural factors are seen in balance.

A comparative analysis of these three schools shows that the formation of a life strategy is a complex process consisting of the integration of a person's internal psychological resources, motivation, reflective abilities, social experience and spiritual values. Therefore, a systematic study of theoretical views on the formation of life strategies in students creates a solid methodological basis for further research.

An analysis of the Western, CIS and Uzbek psychological literature on this issue

shows that the concept of “life strategy” does not have a single, generally accepted definition, but is interpreted differently within different scientific schools. This situation, on the one hand, indicates that the category is complex and multifaceted in content, and on the other hand, it also creates methodological uncertainties in studying the problem of the formation of life strategies in students.

Determining the content of the concept of life strategies in students requires, first of all, consideration of the aspects inherent in the study of this phenomenon from a socio-psychological perspective. Since the issue of life strategies is inextricably linked with the development of the individual, his conscious determination of his own path and his formation as an active subject in society, its analysis becomes one of the main research areas of social psychology. At the same time, since this issue is located at the intersection of two “parent” disciplines - general psychology and sociology - the study of life strategies in students requires a specific scientific approach. General psychology considers the social conditioning of the individual, how he assimilates and reproduces social experience, how he manifests his individuality in existing conditions. In this case, the main attention is paid to the internal processes of the individual, the mechanisms of psychic development. The social psychological approach studies this process in a broader context - inextricably linked to how a person is formed in specific groups, communities and educational environments. When a student develops a life strategy, it is these social groups, communication systems, the educational process and the influence of peers that play a decisive role.

In the sociological approach, the individual is seen more as a certain social type of society, an element of the social structure. This approach helps to understand how macro-specialized factors - the education system, the labor market, social institutions, cultural values - influence the formation of a student's life strategy. Although sociology does not delve deeply into the individuality of a student, it identifies external factors that determine his choices, opportunities and directions.

The different views of social psychological approaches and its "parent" disciplines - general psychology and sociology - on the study of personality are also clearly manifested in the analysis of the issue of forming life strategies in students. Each approach focuses on different aspects of life strategies, thereby allowing for a comprehensive study of this phenomenon.

From the point of view of general psychology, life strategies are studied primarily in connection with the internal, subjective and individual structural elements of the individual. In this approach, the student's activity, sense of responsibility, level of understanding of the meaning of life, motivation, volitional qualities, personal decisions and the formation of his own "I" occupy a central place. That is, general psychology analyzes the student's life strategy through his inner world, mental processes and personal experience. This helps to understand how the strategy is formed

in the student's mind, through what internal mechanisms it arises.

The specific aspects of studying life strategies from a socio-psychological perspective, in our opinion, are determined by two main principles. First, such an analysis must take into account social concreteness. That is, students' life strategies should be considered as ways of constructing a life path that they choose and implement as representatives of a certain social group of which they are a member. These strategies are not formed randomly; they arise in close connection with specific socio-economic conditions, such as the educational system, economic opportunities, labor market requirements, family and cultural environment. Therefore, in order to understand the strategies chosen by students, it is necessary to take into account the real conditions and social context in which they live.

The second principle is to address human individuality in the study of life strategies, that is, to take into account the student's specific psychological characteristics, values, motives and personal development directions. Each student, despite living in the same social conditions, builds a life strategy differently. Therefore, the following questions are important when analyzing the strategy:

- To what extent do these social conditions create an opportunity to form the student's individuality?
- How consciously does the student implement his subjective position in the process of designing his life path?
- What aspects of individuality do his choices, decisions and life plans reflect?
- What specific psychological methods does the student use in implementing his life strategy?

So, in the socio-psychological study of students' life strategies, two directions come together: on the one hand, it relies on real socio-economic conditions; on the other hand, it seeks to explain how the student's individuality, his personal position, is manifested. Since life strategy is a process that occurs as a result of the combination of social influences and personal goals, it is precisely through this integrative approach that its full understanding is possible.

Adequate coverage of the specific features of the socio-psychological study of life strategies requires, first of all, determining the place of this phenomenon in the problems of the social psychology of the individual. The student's life strategy is a way of consciously organizing his life path and is one of the most important psychological mechanisms regulating the social behavior of the individual. It ensures the integrity of the individual's life, harmonizes the content of his life, goals and directions.

From this point of view, the life strategy of students can be considered as a component of the socialization process. Because the life strategy directly affects the process of the student's entry into society, mastering roles in it, internalizing social norms and values. In the process of formation as an active member of society, it is

through his life strategy that the student finds his place in the social environment, manifests his individuality, and consciously assimilates social experience.

In our opinion, the life strategy is manifested as a factor determining a certain direction in the student's socialization. It determines not only how the student adapts to society, but also the paths and nature of this process. For example, a student with an active, goal-oriented and planned life strategy actively manages the socialization process: he chooses social roles that are consistent with his goals, develops the necessary competencies, and consciously enters into social relationships. On the contrary, a student whose life strategy is unclear or randomly formed takes a passive path in socialization, develops under the random influence of external factors.

Conclusion.

In general, the analysis of the literature shows that, although the issue of the formation of life strategies in students has been covered to a certain extent by various scientific schools, a complex, systematic, integrative approach is lacking. This monograph aims to fill this gap and develop a holistic psychological model of the formation of life strategies in students based on various theoretical approaches. Thus, the analysis and discussion of the literature conducted in paragraph 1.3 serves as a methodological foundation for the empirical study of students' life strategies in the following chapters, the identification of psychological mechanisms, and the development of practical recommendations.

List of used literature:

1. Ananyev B.G. Psychology of personality. — M.: Pedagogical, 1990. — 320 p.
2. Vygotsky L.S. Psychology of human development. — M.: Prosveshchenie, 1984. — 432 p.
3. Levin L.I. Psychology of thinking and activity. — M.: Nauka, 1988. — 288 p.
4. Zhdanov A.A. Psychology and life strategy. — SPb.: Peter, 2005. — 256 p.
5. Bandura A. Self-efficacy: The exercise of control. — New York: W.H. Freeman, 1997. — 604 p.
6. Demidova E.A. Formirovanie jiznennyx strategii u studentov // Vestnik psichologii i pedagogiki. — 2012. — No. 3. — S. 45–52.
7. Rubinstein S.L. Basic public psychology. — M.: Yurayt, 2000. — 512 p.
8. Kovalev V.V. Psychological mechanism of decision-making in the educational environment. — M.: Academy, 2010. — 224 p.